

Cloud Computing: A Survey & Challenges

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Abstract: In this paper we have presented an overview of the technique Cloud computing. We have conducted a survey to study more about this technology and have reviewed the various challenges & applications related to this technology

Keywords: Cluster, Grid, Public clouds, Private clouds.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last several decades, advancements in computational techniques, storage, and networking technology have allowed us to generate, process, and share increasing amounts of information in new ways. As new applications of computing technology are developed and introduced, these applications are often used in ways that their designers never envisioned. New applications, in turn, leads to new demands for even more powerful computing infrastructure. To meet these computing-infrastructure demands, system designers are constantly looking for new system architectures and algorithms to process larger collections of data more quickly than is feasible with today's systems.

The establishment of computing systems from large numbers of commodity components leads to some significant challenges like infrastructure, support, costing of establishment etc.,. Software challenges also arise in this environment because development of software that can address the complete need of computing power of many machines is far more difficult than writing software for a single, faster machine.

To address these challenges a number of commercial and academic organizations have come up to built large systems from commodity computers, disks, and networks. The organizations have developed variety of novel approaches to address the challenges outlined above. In some cases, these organizations have used their hardware and software to provide storage, computational, and data management services to their own internal users, or to provide these services to external customers for a fee. To refer hardware and software environment that implements this service-based environment is known as a *cloud computing* environment.

Cloud computing is a computing paradigm, where a large pool of systems are connected in private or public networks, to provide dynamically scalable infrastructure for application, data and file storage. With the advent of this technology, the cost of computation, application hosting, content storage and delivery has reduced significantly.

2. NOMENCLATURE

In of cloud computing a computing *cluster* consists of a collection of similar or identical machines that physically sit in the same computer room or building. Each machine in the cluster is a complete computer consisting of one or more CPUs, memory, disk drives, and network interfaces. The machines are networked together via one or more high-speed local area networks. Another important characteristic of a cluster is that it's owned and operated by a single administrative entity such as a research center or a company.

Finally, the software used to program and manage clusters should give users the illusion hat they're interacting with a single large computer when in reality the cluster may consist of hundreds or thousands of individual machines. Clusters are typically used for scientific or commercial applications that can be parallelized. Since clusters can be built out of commodity components, they are often less expensive to construct and operate than supercomputers.

Although the term *grid* is sometimes used interchangeably with cluster, a computational grid takes somewhat different approach to high performance computing. A grid typically consists of a collection of heterogeneous machines that are geographically distributed. As with a cluster, each machine is a complete computer, and the machines are connected via high-speed networks. Because a grid is geographically distributed, some of the machines are connected via wide-area networks that may have less bandwidth and/or higher latency than machines sitting in the same computer room. Another important distinction between a grid and a cluster is that the machines that constitute a grid may not all be owned by the same administrative entity. Consequently, grids typically provide services to authenticate and authorize users to access resources on a remote set of machines on the

same grid. Because researchers in the physical sciences often use grids to collect, process, and disseminate data, grid software provides services to perform bulk transfers of large files between sites. Since a computation may involve moving data between sites and performing different computations on the data, grids usually provide mechanisms for managing long-running jobs across all of the machines in the grid.

3. CLOUD COMPUTING MODELS

Cloud Providers offer services that can be grouped into three categories.

3.1. Software as a Service (SaaS): In this model, a complete application is offered to the customer, as a service on demand. A single instance of the service runs on the cloud & multiple end users are serviced. On the customers' side, there is no need for upfront investment in servers or software licenses, while for the provider, the costs are lowered, since only a single application needs to be hosted & maintained.

3.2B. Platform as a Service (PaaS): Here, a layer of software, or development environment is encapsulated & offered as a service, upon which other higher levels of service can be built. The customer has the freedom to build his own applications, which run on the provider's infrastructure. To meet manageability and scalability requirements of the applications, PaaS providers offer a predefined combination of OS and application servers, such as LAMP platform (Linux, Apache, MySQL and PHP), restricted J2EE, Ruby etc. Google's App Engine, Force.com, etc are some of the popular PaaS examples.

3.3. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): IaaS provides basic storage and computing capabilities as standardized services over the network. Servers, storage systems, networking equipment, data centre space etc. are pooled and made available to handle workloads. The customer would typically deploy his own software on the infrastructure. Some common examples are Amazon, GoGrid, 3 Tera, etc.

4. CLASSIFICATION OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE CLOUDS

Enterprises can choose to deploy applications on Public, Private or Hybrid clouds. Cloud Integrators can play a vital part in determining the right cloud path for each organization.

4.1. Public Cloud

Public clouds are owned and operated by third parties; they deliver superior economies of scale to customers, as the infrastructure costs are spread among a mix of users, giving

each individual client an attractive low-cost, "Pay-as-you-go" model. All customers share the same infrastructure pool with limited configuration, security protections, and availability variances. These are managed and supported by the cloud provider. One of the advantages of a Public cloud is that they may be larger than an enterprises cloud, thus providing the ability to scale seamlessly, on demand.

4.2. Private Cloud

Private clouds are built exclusively for a single enterprise. They aim to address concerns on data security and offer greater control, which is typically lacking in a public cloud. There are two variations to a private cloud:

1. **On-premise Private Cloud:** On-premise private clouds, also known as internal clouds are hosted within one's own data center. This model provides a more standardized process and protection, but is limited in aspects of size and scalability. IT departments would also need to incur the capital and operational costs for the physical resources. This is best suited for applications which require complete control and configurability of the infrastructure and security.
2. **Externally hosted Private Cloud:** This type of private cloud is hosted externally with a cloud provider, where the provider facilitates an exclusive cloud environment with full guarantee of privacy. This is best suited for enterprises that don't prefer a public cloud due to sharing of physical resources.
3. **Hybrid Cloud:** Hybrid Clouds combine both public and private cloud models. With a Hybrid Cloud, service providers can utilize 3rd party Cloud Providers in a full or partial manner thus increasing the flexibility of computing. The Hybrid cloud environment is capable of providing on-demand, externally provisioned scale. The ability to augment a private cloud with the resources of a public cloud can be used to manage any unexpected surges in workload.

5. CLOUD COMPUTING BENEFITS

Enterprises would need to align their applications, so as to exploit the architecture models that Cloud Computing offers. Some of the typical benefits are listed below:

1. **Reduced Cost:** There are a number of reasons to attribute Cloud technology with lower costs. The billing model is pay as per usage; the infrastructure is not purchased thus lowering maintenance. Initial expense and recurring expenses are much lower than traditional computing.

2. **Increased Storage:** With the massive Infrastructure that is offered by Cloud providers today, storage & maintenance of large volumes of data is a reality. Sudden workload spikes are also managed effectively & efficiently, since the cloud can scale dynamically.
3. **Flexibility:** This is an extremely important characteristic. With enterprises having to adapt, even more rapidly, to changing business conditions, speed to deliver is critical. Cloud computing stresses on getting applications to market very quickly, by using the most appropriate building blocks necessary for deployment.
3. **Management Capabilities:** Despite there being multiple cloud providers, the management of platform and infrastructure is still in its infancy. Features like Auto-scaling□ for example, are a crucial requirement for many enterprises. There is huge potential to improve on the scalability and load balancing features provided today.
4. **Regulatory and Compliance Restrictions:** In some of the European countries, Government regulations do not allow customer's personal information and other sensitive information to be physically located outside the state or country. In order to meet such requirements, cloud providers need to setup a data center or a storage site exclusively within the country to comply with regulations. Having such an infrastructure may not always be feasible and is a big challenge for cloud providers.

6. CLOUD COMPUTING CHALLENGES

Despite its growing influence, concerns regarding cloud computing still remain. In our opinion, the benefits outweigh the drawbacks and the model is worth exploring. Some common challenges are:

1. **Data Protection Data Security** is a crucial element that warrants scrutiny. Enterprises are reluctant to buy an assurance of business data security from vendors. They fear losing data to competition and the data confidentiality of consumers. In many instances, the actual storage location is not disclosed, adding onto the security concerns of enterprises. In the existing models, firewalls across data centers (owned by enterprises) protect this sensitive information. In the cloud model, Service providers are responsible for maintaining data security and enterprises would have to rely on them.
2. **Data Recovery and Availability:** All business applications have Service level agreements that are stringently followed. Operational teams play a key role in management of service level agreements and runtime governance of applications. In production environments, operational teams support appropriate clustering and fail over Data Replication System monitoring (Transactions monitoring, logs monitoring and others) Maintenance (Runtime Governance) Disaster recovery Capacity and performance management. If, any of the above mentioned services is under-served by a cloud provider, the damage & impact could be severe.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have presented an overview of the Cloud computing Technology & the its application in various engineering research areas. We have carried out our survey in a controlled environment & thus can conclude that it is definitely an area for further research.

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